

NEWSLETTER

Welcome to **CONCILIARE: Advancing Our Research**

Welcome to the third edition of the CONCILIARE newsletter!

Dear colleagues, as our project progresses, we are pleased to share updates on our activities, upcoming events, and new resources. This newsletter aims to serve as a platform to promote the project's activities, parallel events, and ongoing research, keeping partners and collaborators informed and connected.

PAST EVENTS

CONCILIARE Annual Meeting 2025

The CONCILIARE Annual Meeting took place from **March 19th to 20th, 2025**, at the **Institute of Social Sciences Ivo Pilar**, in **Zagreb, Croatia**. It was a fruitful opportunity to share updates on ongoing research, strengthen collaborations among partners, and reflect on the challenges and achievements of the project.

📷 Photos of the event are available on the project's website and social media channels.

Research Seminar in Brussels

The research seminar "Towards the Psychosocial Reappropriation and Resocialization by the Source Communities of Katanga of the Remains of Ancestors to Be Repatriated and Cultural Objects to Be Recovered", organized within the PRD-ARES project (ULB–UNILU–UCLouvain) with the support of CRHIDI and CONCILIARE, took place on March 28th, 2025, at Université libre de Bruxelles.

CONCILIARE Presentation at the University of Coimbra

On April 2nd, 2025, CONCILIARE was presented by Joaquim Pires Valentim during the visit of the Administration and Executive Coordinators of the University of Coimbra to the Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences.

UPCOMING EVENTS

Colonial (De)Visions: Dialogues in Visual Culture, Alterities and Artivisms

A joint event by CONCILIARE, MigraMediaActs, and the SOPCOM Visual Culture Working Group, held in Portuguese and English, that explores the intersections between visual culture, memory, colonial heritage and activism, through guided tours, film screenings, and roundtable discussions. In-person and online participation options available.

 April 28, 2025

 Braga, Portugal

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Seminar with Wolfgang Wagner

Wolfgang Wagner (University of Tartu) will conduct a seminar titled “Essentialism in Intergroup Relations: Stereotyping and Fear of Mixing Essence”, in collaboration with CONCILIARE and the Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences of the University of Coimbra.

 May 6, 2025

 Coimbra, Portugal

NEWS

Collaboration with the Portuguese Press Association

The CONCILIARE team at the University of Coimbra has initiated a collaboration with the Portuguese Press Association. Two chronicles have already been published and distributed nationwide through the regional press:

- “*Changing Perspective: the role of literature of originary peoples*” by PhD student Gabriella Andrietta
- “*Colonial emotions: the legacy that we insist to ignore*” by PhD student Ana Cabrita

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Thank you for your continued support and engagement in CONCILIARE!

Best regards,

Júlia Vilhena, Rosa Cabecinhas, Teresa Forte and Emiliano Abad

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